

1 **Ahnak and Larp4b ribonucleoproteins are mobilized during trophectoderm commitment in the**
2 **human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here mobilization of
9 Ahnak and Larp4b ribonucleoproteins during lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human
10 embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Küspert, M., Murakawa, Y., Schäffler, K., Vanselow, J.T., Wolf, E., Juranek, S., Schlosser, A.,
13 Landthaler, M. and Fischer, U., 2015. LARP4B is an AU-rich sequence associated factor that promotes
14 mRNA accumulation and translation. *Rna*, 21(7), pp.1294-1305.